

**RESULTS OF EXPERIMENTAL AND TEST WORK ON PLANNING
THE OBJECTIVES OF THE TRAINING SESSIONS OF THE SUBJECT
“PROBABILITY THEORY AND MATHEMATICAL STATISTICS” AND
ESTABLISHING AN INTERDISCIPLINARY CONNECTION IN THE
TEACHING OF THIS SCIENCE**

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Annotation: The results of experimental work on planning the objectives of training sessions in the discipline "Probability theory and mathematical statistics". Considering that the methods of analysis of economic processes and the methods used in teaching mathematics have much in common, and also, taking into account the possibility of implementing integrative links at the level of activities.

Keywords: mathematical modeling, integrative quality, mathematical abilities

The following intellectual skills can be distinguished as general methods of educational activity that students should master when studying mathematics and disciplines of the financial and economic cycle and their components:

- understanding of algorithms for solving economic problems (problem statement, selection of necessary information for its solution, analysis of the problem situation, hypotheses);
- ability to mathematical modeling (determination of data, conditions and boundaries of the search for solutions, translation of the problem into the language of mathematics, application or construction of an adequate mathematical apparatus, interpretation of the solution);
- ability to think logically (deductive and inductive reasoning, combination of logic and intuition, argumentation of conclusions and conclusions);
- communication skills (reading, writing, speaking in the language of mathematics, the use of mathematical symbols and formulas, the construction of graphs, diagrams, diagrams);

- ability to apply new information technologies. Statistics» and the establishment of interdisciplinary communication in the teaching of this discipline

In the educational process of training in the chosen economic specialty, the future graduate of the university studies a fairly wide list of academic disciplines., The expansion and deepening of scientific knowledge, reflected in modern curricula, are accompanied by increased disunity and weakening of ties between the subjects studied, which to a certain extent leads to a decrease in the effectiveness of the cognitive process and the quality of training, including the number of highly qualified economists. At the same time, the requirements for their level of training, defined by the State Educational Standard of Higher Professional Education, are quite high and the entire educational process in all its variety of forms is designed to reveal to students not only the interdisciplinary connections of individual academic disciplines, including mathematical, commonality in approaches both in methodological and methodological terms. Also the level of integrity of knowledge based on integrative quality and integrative orientation.

The main sections of mathematics for economic specialties of universities, defined by the federal component in the State Educational Standard of Higher Professional Education, are as follows: analytical geometry and linear algebra; sequences and series; differential and integral calculus; vector analysis and elements of field theory; harmonic analysis; differential equations; numerical methods; functions of a complex variable; elements of functional analysis; probability and statistics: probability theory, random processes, statistical estimation and hypothesis testing, statistical methods of experimental data processing.

The teaching of this course plays an important role in the expansion of scientific and methodological links between mathematics and special disciplines at the Faculty of Agriculture. The main objectives of this course are:

- students' study of modern mathematical language, symbols and mathematical apparatus;

- presentation of the main theoretical provisions, rules and algorithms for solving applied mathematical problems;
- modeling of applied mathematical problems, based on the expansion of philosophical and ideological ideas about objective reality.
- development of logical and spatial thinking among students of the agrarian faculty, as well as mathematical abilities to see, observe, compare various objects, which allows students to develop attention, memory and interests through solving applied problems.

$$\sum_{n=1}^{\infty} p_n = \sum_{n=1}^{\infty} 2^{-n} = 1.$$

So, when constructing probabilistic models in examples we essentially used the physical nature of the objects with which the experiments were conducted – the coin and the bone were “correct” (symmetrical), and only this property allowed us to attribute the same probabilities to all elementary outcomes. If a bent coin is tossed,

then determining the probability p of the coat of arms falling out, based on an equation describing the dynamics of the flight of a rotating irregular coin and the regularities of its elastic collision with the surface, is a very difficult and hardly solvable task.

$$P(A) = 1 - P(A^c)$$

The proposed structure does not contradict the modern direction of improving educational activities in terms of creating an intra-university quality management system for training specialists. The formation of control procedures for assessing the quality of education, starting from the moment of admission to a higher educational institution, is laid down in the expanded calendar and thematic plan of the discipline. It is also provided that the necessary amount of knowledge is brought to the student in a form convenient for him. The educational program, for example, in mathematics, which determines the content of lectures, practical

classes, seminars, is implemented both in the lower limits of the volume of skills and abilities, forming the base of the portfolio of competencies, and in the upper limits of knowledge and skills, providing the initial stage of the continuous formation of a competent graduate of an educational institution.

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